

2 Layered transition metal molybdates as new slow-release
3 micronutrient fertilizer matrices for Zn, Cu and Mo

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11 **Abstract**

12 Micronutrient availability in agricultural soils is an important driver for crop production and for mobile
13 micronutrients, slow-release fertilizers can more efficiently enhance crop nutrition. In this study, for the
14 first time, layered transition metal molybdates (LTMs) are proposed as slow-release fertilizer compounds
15 for the micronutrients molybdenum (Mo), zinc (Zn) and copper (Cu). A series of LTMs was successfully
16 prepared in varying synthesis conditions, characterized (ICP-OES, XRD, FTIR, SEM) and tested for solubility
17 in water. For three selected LTMs (Zn-Mo, Cu-Mo, and Zn-Cu-Mo), the solubility as a function of solution
18 pH was determined. The LTMs showed limited stability in acidic conditions. Therefore, co-compaction of
19 LTMs with pH neutral or alkaline macronutrient carriers (muriate of potash (MOP), limestone, rock
20 phosphate) was explored. A Zn-based LTM co-compacted in a MOP carrier showed a useful slow and
21 almost constant release rate of both Mo and Zn in a column dissolution test (Mo release reaching 32%
22 after 72 h), while a reference compacted MOP fertilizer with soluble Mo released 90% of Mo after 4 h.
23 Hence, a Zn-LTM could prove useful as a slow-release fertilizer or raw material to incorporate into non-
24 acidic macronutrient fertilizers.

25 **Keywords**

26 Layered transition metal molybdate (LTM), slow-release fertilizer, micronutrient, plant nutrition,

27 molybdenum, zinc

28 Introduction

29 The availability of micronutrients in soils is a prominent factor determining agricultural productivity. Crop
30 production systems in soils that are deficient in micronutrients suffer from reduced yields, while a low
31 micronutrient content in feed and food products also undermines the nutritional value ¹. Hence, the
32 application of micronutrients in the form of mineral fertilizers is an important tool to safeguard global
33 food production, both in terms of quantitative and qualitative aspects. Most common micronutrient
34 fertilizers are soluble compounds and often these compounds are co-granulated with macronutrient
35 compounds to ensure a homogeneous micronutrient application to the field ²⁻⁴.

36 Recently, slow-release compounds gained interest as alternatives to soluble fertilizers, aiming *i)* to
37 improve the nutrient use efficiency by aligning nutrient release from the fertilizer with nutrient uptake by
38 the crops, and *ii)* to limit losses of nutrients to the environment (groundwater, surface water,
39 atmosphere). To slow the release of micronutrients, two distinct approaches have been identified. Firstly,
40 conventional soluble compounds can be coated with polymers to slow down micronutrient release, either
41 by coating the co-granulated product containing both macronutrients and micronutrients, or by
42 encapsulating only the micronutrient compound ^{5,6}. Secondly, compounds with an intrinsic reduced
43 solubility can be used. Both natural sparingly-soluble minerals ⁷ and novel engineered compounds (*e.g.*
44 zeolites, biochar, graphene oxide) have been tested for this application ⁸⁻¹¹. More recently, layered double
45 hydroxides (LDHs) have gained significant interest as fertilizer compounds for slow release of nutrients.
46 These are layered metal hydroxide materials of divalent and trivalent cations containing electrostatically-
47 bound interlayer anions which can slow the release of (i) cationic micronutrients (*e.g.* Zn, Cu) via
48 controlled dissolution and (ii) anionic micronutrients (*e.g.* B, Mo), via exchange with counter anions from
49 the soil solution and also via LDH dissolution ¹²⁻¹⁵.

50 Interestingly, while several in-depth studies have investigated LDHs for slow-release fertilizer application
51 ^{16,17}, layered transition metal molybdates (LTM) have not yet been proposed. The composition of LTMs is
52 defined by the general formula $AT_2OH(MoO_4)_2(H_2O)$, with T^{2+} representing a divalent transition metal
53 cation (*e.g.* Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+}) and A^+ representing a monovalent cation (*e.g.* NH_4^+ , K^+). Thus, both LTMs
54 and LDHs are inorganic, layered, metal hydroxide materials, and their similar nature is illustrated by the
55 synthesis pathways that link these two phases ^{18,19}. However, important differences also exist between
56 Mo-LDHs and LTMs, which can strongly influence their chemical behavior. As opposed to LDHs, LTMs do
57 not contain trivalent cations (*e.g.* Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+}). In LDHs, the presence of trivalent cations is responsible for
58 the net positive charge of the metal hydroxide layers and, consequently, LDHs can act as anion exchangers
59 to electrostatically bind molybdate anions in the interlayer gallery. In LTMs, molybdate anions are not
60 bound electrostatically, but bind to the layers themselves through shared Mo-O-T bonds ¹⁸. With this
61 arrangement, the LTM layers bear a net negative charge and, hence, LTMs act as cation exchangers and
62 electrostatically bind A^+ cations in the interlayer gallery (*e.g.* K^+ , NH_4^+ , Na^+). Two structural polytypes of
63 the LTM material class have been identified ^{20,21}, *i.e.* one structure characterized by chains of edge-sharing
64 transition metal octahedra interconnected by molybdate tetrahedra (referred to as the Φ_x structure) and
65 one structure characterized by sheets of edge-sharing transition metal octahedra with molybdate
66 tetrahedra binding on cation vacancy sites (referred to as the Φ_y structure). To date, LTM materials have
67 been successfully synthesized with a range of divalent transition metals, including Zn, Cu, Ni, Co, and Mn
68 ^{19,22-27}. In addition, next to the class of LTMs, similar materials have been described in which the Mo
69 position is occupied by other elements, *e.g.* V or Se ^{28,29}.

70 Here, LTM materials of Zn and/or Cu are proposed as promising new slow-release micronutrient fertilizer
71 compounds. A sparingly-soluble LTM material could guarantee a slow release of Mo, and also supply
72 accompanying cationic micronutrients Zn and Cu. Thus, with the application of LTM to soil at
73 recommended Mo rates, a part of the plants' requirement for Zn and Cu will also be supplied using this

74 product. Furthermore, the absence of trivalent cations in LTM materials can be considered a benefit for a
75 fertilizer application in comparison with Mo-LDH materials, since trivalent cations from LDHs make little
76 or no contribution to plant nutrition. Lastly, high anion concentrations in a macronutrient carrier
77 environment could jeopardize slow Mo release from Mo-LDH fertilizers by strongly enhancing the MoO_4^{2-}
78 exchange ¹⁵. In LTMs, the release of Mo is controlled by dissolution of the LTM, and therefore less likely
79 to be affected by the macronutrient carrier.

80 In the current study, a series of LTM materials was prepared in varying synthesis conditions. Subsequently,
81 the LTM materials were characterized with XRD, FTIR, and SEM, and tested for solubility in water. For a
82 selection of promising LTM materials, the solubility was investigated in more detail with respect to *i)* the
83 dependency of the solution pH and *ii)* the influence of different macronutrient carrier environments.
84 Finally, the global potassium fertilizer, compacted muriate of potash (MOP) was enhanced with the
85 incorporation of a LTM compound and in a column dissolution experiment, the Mo release was compared
86 with that of MOP containing a conventional soluble Mo fertilizer.

87

88 **Materials and methods**

89 ***LTM synthesis and characterization***

90 The synthesis of LTM materials was performed according to a precipitation method adapted from Mitchell
91 *et al.* ¹⁹. In brief, an aqueous precursor solution was prepared by dissolving 7 mmol of a transition metal
92 T^{2+} salt and 7 mmol Mo (as $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in 50 mL MilliQ water. The precipitation was performed
93 at room temperature with the dropwise addition of an alkaline solution to the precursor solution until a
94 constant desired pH value (6.0-8.0, see below) was obtained. Subsequently, the suspension was aged by
95 mixing at room temperature for 4 h, after which the precipitate was recovered via centrifugation, washed
96 three times with MilliQ water, and dried at 60°C. According to this general procedure, a series of LTM

97 materials was prepared by varying the choice of T^{2+} (Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , or an equimolar mixture of Zn^{2+} and Cu^{2+}),
98 the T^{2+} salt that was used in the precursor solution (either nitrate salts $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$,
99 or chloride salts $ZnCl_2$ and $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$), the alkaline solution used for titration (KOH or NH_4OH , 1 M), and
100 the drying method (room temperature or $60^\circ C$). For a successful precipitation, titration for the synthesis
101 with Zn was performed to pH 8.0, the synthesis with Cu to pH 6.0, and the synthesis with both Zn and Cu
102 to pH 8.0. The N content of the obtained materials was determined with C:N analysis (Thermo Fisher
103 Scientific FlashEA 1112 HT) and the Zn, Cu, Mo and K content with Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical
104 Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES; PerkinElmer Optima 3300 DV) after digestion in *aqua regia*. The
105 chemical formulae of the prepared LTMs were calculated from the measured composition of interlayered
106 cations A^+ , transition metals T^{2+} and Mo, while the stoichiometry of the protons was calculated from the
107 charge balance between the T^{2+} -Mo hydroxide layers and the interlayer cations³⁰. The crystallographic
108 characteristics of the materials were investigated with powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), performed with a
109 Malvern PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer in transmission mode, using a PIXcel3D solid state detector
110 and Cu anode (Cu $K\alpha_1$: 1.5406 Å; Cu $K\alpha_2$: 1.5444 Å) at a scan rate of $2.2^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$ and a scan range of 1.3-
111 70° . Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis was performed with an Alpha FT-IR spectrometer (Bruker
112 Optics, Germany), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis with a Quanta 450 (FEI, USA)
113 microscope on Pt-coated samples.

114

115 ***LTM solubility in water***

116 The water-solubility of the LTM materials was determined in a short dissolution experiment. The LTMs
117 were added to 5 mL MilliQ water at a liquid:solid ratio of 100 mL g^{-1} (duplicate treatment). The suspensions
118 were shaken end-over-end for 2 h, after which the supernatants were collected via centrifugation. The
119 solutions were filtered (0.45 μm) and analyzed by ICP-OES and continuous flow colorimetric

120 ammonium/nitrate analysis (Skalar SA-40). Also the pH of the unfiltered solutions was measured. With
121 this procedure, it was not confirmed if equilibrium was obtained, yet it allowed the screening of the
122 different materials. Hence, for a selection of three prepared LTMs (products from Zn, Cu and Zn/Cu
123 chloride precursor solutions with NH_4OH titration and oven-drying at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the solubility in water was
124 determined as a function of the pH. For this, the LTMs were added to 15 mL MilliQ water at a liquid:solid
125 ratio of 60 mL g^{-1} . After stirring for 10 min, the pH of the suspension was measured and a 1.5 mL sample
126 of the solution was taken and filtered ($0.45\text{ }\mu\text{m}$). Then, 1.5 mL of a 0.05 M HNO_3 solution was added to
127 the mixed LTM suspension and the suspension was stirred for 10 min. This process of pH measurement,
128 solution sampling and further acidification was repeated until a pH was reached at which all LTM material
129 dissolved. The filtered samples were analyzed for Mo, Zn and Cu with ICP-OES.

130

131 ***LTM solubility in macronutrient carrier environments***

132 The solubility of the three selected LTM materials was determined in the presence of alkaline
133 macronutrient fertilizer compounds muriate of potash (MOP, Esterhazy, Canada), rock phosphate
134 (Bayovar, Peru), and commercial limestone, and the LTM solubility was compared with that in water. The
135 LTM materials were incubated in MilliQ water at a fertilizer:LTM weight ratio of 10 g g^{-1} and a liquid:solid
136 ratio of 100 mL g^{-1} (duplicate treatment). The suspensions were shaken end-over-end for 24 h, after which
137 the supernatants were collected via centrifugation. The solid material obtained was dried at 60°C and
138 analyzed using XRD. The solutions were filtered ($0.45\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) and analyzed using ICP-OES for Mo, Zn and Cu,
139 and also the pH of the unfiltered solutions was measured. Finally, the acid-base properties of MOP
140 fertilizer, raw Esterhazy potash ore and analytical-grade KCl were determined. For this, these materials
141 were shaken in MilliQ water for 2 h (liquid:solid ratio of 10 mL g^{-1}), and the pH of the obtained solutions
142 was measured.

143

144 ***LTM column dissolution test***

145 A column dissolution experiment was performed to determine the kinetics of the Mo release from a
146 compacted pelletized LTM-MOP fertilizer compared to that from a pelletized MOP fertilizer containing
147 soluble Mo. The LTM-MOP fertilizer was prepared by thoroughly mixing sieved Zn-Mo LTM powder and
148 MOP powder (<250 μm) using pestle and mortar, wetting the mixture with deionized water (150 $\mu\text{L g}^{-1}$
149 dry powder) and pelletizing in a manual pill press to obtain a product containing 0.5% Mo (pellet diameter
150 4 mm, average weight 55 mg). The soluble Mo reference fertilizer was prepared the same way from a
151 mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (amMo) with MOP (also containing ~0.5% Mo). Finally, pelletized MOP (no
152 added Mo) was also included as a control fertilizer. The Mo contents of the LTM-MOP and the amMo-
153 MOP fertilizers were determined by digestion of five individual pellets in HNO_3 , and subsequent analysis
154 by ICP-OES.

155 The column experiment was performed according to the method of Baird *et al.*³¹. In brief, for each
156 fertilizer, 1 g of pellets was placed in a polypropylene column (150 mm \times 15 mm) held in place by acid-
157 washed glass wool (duplicate treatment). Using a peristaltic pump, deionized water was introduced at the
158 bottom of the column at a rate of 10 mL h^{-1} , while for 72 h the eluate containing dissolved nutrient was
159 collected using an automated fraction collector (Gilson FC 204). The eluate samples were analyzed with
160 ICP-OES for Mo, K and Zn, and also the pH of the eluate samples was measured.

161

162 **Results and discussion**

163 ***LTM material characterization***

164 Using the range of synthesis conditions, LTM materials were successfully prepared, as evidenced by XRD,
165 FTIR, and elemental analysis (Fig. 1, Fig. S1, Table 1). The elemental composition of all materials was in
166 line with that of a LTM phase (Table 1) and, furthermore, demonstrated the consistency of LTM synthesis
167 with the current uncomplicated precipitation method. The molar $A^+:\text{Mo}$ ratio of the materials ranged
168 between 0.50 and 0.74, and the molar $T^{2+}:\text{Mo}$ ratio between 1.12 and 1.35. The choice of metal salt and
169 the drying method had only a very limited effect on the elemental composition of the material obtained.
170 The synthesis with single transition metals resulted in slightly more incorporated Cu in comparison with
171 Zn for most corresponding synthesis conditions. The same trend was present for the mixed-metal
172 synthesis procedures, where Zn-Cu LTMs contained slightly more Cu than Zn. The use of NH_4OH as an
173 alkaline source for the precipitation resulted in a slightly higher A^+ content (formula stoichiometry
174 between 1.31 and 1.48) in comparison with the use of KOH (stoichiometry between 0.99 and 1.19), which
175 could be attributed to a difference in sorption strength between NH_4^+ and K^+ , *e.g.* due to possible
176 hydrogen bonding with NH_4^+ and not with K^+ in the interlayer gallery.

177 Table 1: The chemical formulae of the LTM materials prepared from different metal salts, titration with different alkali, and drying at room temperature (RT) or
 178 60°C. The stoichiometry of the interlayered cations A^+ (NH_4 and/or K), the transition metals T^{2+} (Zn and/or Cu), and Mo in the formulae was determined via
 179 chemical analysis of the materials, while the stoichiometry of the protons was calculated from the charge balance between the T^{2+} -Mo hydroxide layers and the
 180 interlayer cations.

		Nitrate metal salt		Chloride metal salt	
		KOH titration	NH_4OH titration	KOH titration	NH_4OH titration
Zn-Mo	RT	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.22}\text{K}_{0.79}\text{H}_{1.19}\text{Zn}_{2.40}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.34}\text{H}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{2.49}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.30}\text{K}_{0.70}\text{H}_{1.40}\text{Zn}_{2.30}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.32}\text{H}_{1.19}\text{Zn}_{2.25}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$
	60°C	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.21}\text{K}_{0.78}\text{H}_{1.19}\text{Zn}_{2.41}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.33}\text{H}_{0.67}\text{Zn}_{2.50}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.29}\text{K}_{0.72}\text{H}_{1.44}\text{Zn}_{2.28}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.33}\text{H}_{1.16}\text{Zn}_{2.25}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$
Cu-Mo	RT	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.29}\text{K}_{0.71}\text{H}_{0.63}\text{Cu}_{2.69}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.34}\text{H}_{0.55}\text{Cu}_{2.55}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.29}\text{K}_{0.72}\text{H}_{0.75}\text{Cu}_{2.57}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.31}\text{H}_{0.47}\text{Cu}_{2.61}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$
	60°C	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.28}\text{K}_{0.74}\text{H}_{0.59}\text{Cu}_{2.69}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.34}\text{H}_{0.58}\text{Cu}_{2.54}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.34}\text{K}_{0.72}\text{H}_{0.80}\text{Cu}_{2.57}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.32}\text{H}_{0.46}\text{Cu}_{2.61}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$
Zn-Cu-Mo	RT	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.39}\text{K}_{0.75}\text{H}_{0.75}\text{Zn}_{1.20}\text{Cu}_{1.36}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.46}\text{H}_{0.29}\text{Zn}_{1.28}\text{Cu}_{1.34}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.40}\text{K}_{0.68}\text{H}_{0.57}\text{Zn}_{1.29}\text{Cu}_{1.39}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.41}\text{H}_{0.51}\text{Zn}_{1.24}\text{Cu}_{1.30}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$
	60°C	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.39}\text{K}_{0.80}\text{H}_{0.72}\text{Zn}_{1.19}\text{Cu}_{1.35}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.48}\text{H}_{0.28}\text{Zn}_{1.28}\text{Cu}_{1.34}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{0.41}\text{K}_{0.70}\text{H}_{0.68}\text{Zn}_{1.26}\text{Cu}_{1.34}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$	$(\text{NH}_4)_{1.43}\text{H}_{0.45}\text{Zn}_{1.25}\text{Cu}_{1.31}\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{MoO}_4)_2$

181

182 The XRD analysis confirmed a phase-pure LTM phase for most of the synthesized materials, with the
 183 exception of one material without a clear XRD pattern (Fig. 1). With most synthesis procedures, the Φ_y
 184 structural polytype was obtained, while only the synthesis procedures of Zn-based LTMs with KOH as
 185 alkaline source yielded the Φ_x polytype. This structural identity of the materials was in line with earlier
 186 results, namely that the Φ_y polytype has only been reported with NH_4^+ as A^+ , while the Φ_x polytype can
 187 exist with Na^+ , K^+ , or NH_4^+ as A^+ ¹⁹. The FTIR spectra were in line with earlier work ^{22,24}, showing the
 188 presence of *i*) molybdate, with bands associated to the stretching mode of Mo-O and the
 189 stretching/bending modes of Mo-O-Mo ($750\text{-}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), *ii*) water, with bands associated to stretching
 190 mode of O-H (3480 cm^{-1}) and the bending mode of H-O-H (1590 cm^{-1}), and *iii*) NH_4^+ , with bands associated
 191 to an asymmetric stretching mode of N-H ($3000\text{-}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a deformation mode of H-N-H (1380 cm^{-1})
 192 ¹) (Fig. S1).

193

194

195 Fig. 1: The XRD patterns of the different LTM materials prepared by varying the alkaline source (KOH or NH_4OH), the
 196 transition metal (Zn, Cu, or both), the transition metal salt (nitrate or chloride salt), and drying method (room
 197 temperature or 60°C).

198

199 The effect of the transition metal on morphology and size of LTM crystals was investigated by SEM,
200 focusing on the three materials prepared from T^{2+} chloride salts, titration with NH_4OH and drying at $60^\circ C$
201 (Fig. 2). For the Zn-based LTM prepared with this procedure, a layered morphology was observed, with
202 spherical planes and a substantial plate thickness. The size of most crystals ranged between 1-2 μm .
203 However, the crystal size of the Cu-based LTM ($<100\text{ nm}$) appeared to be a lot smaller than that of the Zn-
204 based LTM. While the morphology of the small crystals of the Cu-based LTM could not be determined, the
205 layered nature of this material was also clear. For the Zn-Cu-based LTM, an intermediate crystal size was
206 obtained in comparison with the two other LTMs, with most crystals within the range of 200-400 nm. The
207 trend in crystal size for these three LTMs was in line with the peak sharpness of their XRD patterns (*i.e.*
208 larger crystal sizes were associated with sharper XRD peaks) (Fig. 1). While XRD analysis confirmed pure
209 LTM phases for most of the synthesized materials, one Cu-based material did not show clear XRD
210 reflections. For the synthesis procedures with Cu nitrate salts, drying at room temperature resulted in a
211 better crystallinity than at $60^\circ C$, which could be related to a prolonged crystal forming process at room
212 temperature (~ 3 days). Nonetheless, the apparent morphology and size of crystals of these two Cu-based
213 LTMs were not significantly affected by the drying method (Fig. S2).

214 The Mo content was ~ 1.3 times higher than the Zn content for the Zn-based LTMs, and ~ 1.2 times higher
215 than the Cu content for the Cu-based LTMs. Since application rates of Zn and Cu often are more than
216 tenfold higher than Mo application rates, LTM fertilizer application for Mo nutrition will only supply a
217 fraction ($<10\%$) of the Zn or Cu required by crops.³²

218

219
 220 Fig. 2: The SEM micrographs of the Zn-based (left), Cu-based (two middle) and Zn-Cu-based (two right) LTM materials
 221 prepared from T^{2+} chloride salts, titration with NH_4OH and drying at $60^\circ C$.

222

223 ***LTM batch dissolution in water***

224 The solubility test confirmed that LTMs are sparingly soluble in water (Fig. 3). However, the different LTMs
 225 had very different water solubilities. The highest Mo solubility was obtained for the Zn-based LTMs
 226 prepared with KOH as the alkali, which also suggested a higher intrinsic solubility of the Φ_x polytype
 227 compared to the Φ_y polytype. For the series of LTMs prepared via titration with KOH, the LTM solubility
 228 was strongly linked with the identity of the incorporated T^{2+} , whereas this was less the case for the LTMs
 229 prepared with NH_4OH . While the choice of T^{2+} salt (nitrate vs chloride) had little effect on solubility of the
 230 LTMs obtained from a KOH titration, there was a clear influence for the materials prepared with a NH_4OH
 231 titration, *e.g.* the Zn-based LTMs from a synthesis with Zn chloride showed a lower solubility than those
 232 synthesized with Zn nitrate. The T^{2+} and A^+ dissolution was assessed using the stoichiometry of the LTM
 233 formulae (Table 1), and was expressed as a fraction of the measured Mo dissolution (Fig. S3). This
 234 calculation indicated that the measured Zn release from the Zn-based LTMs was a factor 0.7-0.8 of a
 235 stoichiometric (congruent) dissolution with Mo, while for Cu release from the Cu-based LTMs this was
 236 only a factor of 0.3-0.6. For Zn-Cu-based LTMs, Zn release was near-congruent with Mo, while release of
 237 Cu from these LTMs was negligible. Also the release of interlayer cations A^+ was assessed with respect to

238 the Mo release and the formula of the LTMs. The K release for all LTMs prepared with KOH was near-
239 congruent to that of Mo. However, the release of NH_4 was only stoichiometric for the Zn-based LTMs, and
240 was a factor of 2.2 higher for the Zn-Cu-based LTMs and a factor of 3.7 higher for the Cu-based LTMs in
241 comparison with a stoichiometric dissolution (Fig. S3). Finally, the pH of the solutions ranged between
242 6.2-6.6 for the Zn-based LTMs, between 5.2-5.7 for the Cu-based LTMs, and between 6.1-6.5 for the Zn-
243 Cu-based LTMs (Fig. 3), showing a trend in line with the pH values required for the precipitation of these
244 metals during the LTM synthesis (see materials and methods: titration for the synthesis with Zn to pH 8,
245 the synthesis with Cu to pH 6, and the synthesis with both Zn and Cu to pH 8).

246

247 Fig. 3: The solubility of the LTM materials in water (L:S ratio of 100 mL g⁻¹, 2 h) and the pH of the solutions. Error bars
 248 represent the standard error (n=2).

249 From the series of materials, three LTMs were selected for further assessment, *i.e.* the ones that were
 250 prepared from T²⁺ chloride salts, titration with NH₄OH, and drying at 60°C. This series of LTMs was most
 251 interesting for further assessment because of *i)* their low solubility of Mo in water, particularly of the Zn-
 252 based LTM (Fig. 3), *ii)* the use of NH₄OH for titration of these LTMs, as NH₄OH is a more accessible and
 253 affordable alkali than KOH, and *iii)* the clear XRD characterization for these materials (Fig. 1).

254 The solubility of the three selected LTM materials was assessed with respect to the effect of solution pH (Fig. 4).
 255 Molybdenum and 7^{2+} dissolution in this test (first sampling at intrinsic pH) was in line with that obtained
 256 in the previous water solubility test (Fig. 3), and also the intrinsic pH of the Cu-based LTM was again
 257 significantly lower than that of the two other LTM. The solubility of the Zn-based LTM increased rapidly
 258 with a decreasing solution pH, reaching full dissolution at a pH of 5.3. The dissolution of the Cu-based LTM
 259 was lower than that of the Zn-based LTM, with full dissolution at a pH of 4.0. Interestingly, the dissolution
 260 of the Zn-Cu-based LTM was characterized by a non-stoichiometric dissolution, with mainly Zn and Mo
 261 dissolving within the pH range 6.8-4.5 and Cu and Mo dissolving below pH 4.5.

262
 263 Fig. 4: The solubility of three selected LTM materials as a function of the solution pH at a starting liquid:solid ratio of
 264 60 mL g⁻¹.

265
 266 **LTM solubility in macronutrient carrier environments**

267 Suitable carriers for the application of a slow-release Mo source include important macronutrient fertilizer
 268 compounds used in legume crop production, *i.e.* P and K fertilizers. However, for the use as a carrier for
 269 LTM compounds, acidic fertilizers should be avoided (*e.g.* TSP, MAP) since an acidic environment would
 270 likely strongly enhance LTM dissolution and thus compromise the desired slow release of Mo (Fig. 4).

271 Hence, the solubility of the three LTMs was assessed in the presence of a series of pH neutral and alkaline
272 fertilizer carriers (MOP, rock phosphate and limestone), and compared with their solubility in water (Fig.
273 5a). The equilibrium pH of the MOP solution was 8.9, while the pH of the rock phosphate (RP) suspension
274 was 7.3 and that of the limestone suspension 9.6 (Fig. 5b). The high pH of the MOP fertilizer suspension
275 was surprising, since MOP largely consists of sylvite (KCl mineral), which has no acid-base properties. A
276 separate pH measurement of MOP fertilizer (pH 10.3), Esterhazy potash ore (pH 7.8) and analytical-grade
277 KCl (pH 5.3) showed that the potash ore material is slightly alkaline but also that, during the production
278 of MOP fertilizer from potash ore, the alkalinity of the material is increased. Possibly, this could be related
279 to the addition of alkaline binding agents.

280

281 From a theoretical perspective, the concentration of Mo dissolved from the LTMs in the presence of
282 macronutrient compounds would be determined by the intrinsic LTM solubility and effect of the
283 macronutrient environment on LTM dissolution (pH, ionic strength, solution composition). More
284 specifically, the solubility of species derived from the dissolving LTM phase (*e.g.* the T^{2+} cations) will be an
285 important factor, as re-precipitation of these dissolved species could further sustain LTM dissolution and
286 Mo release. With this test, the lowest Mo concentration was obtained with the Zn-based LTM incubated
287 with MOP (70 μ M Mo). The slightly alkaline character of MOP decreased LTM dissolution, while dissolved
288 species from the LTM remained stable in the MOP solution. However, the limited pH buffer capacity of
289 the MOP matrix was evident from the significant decrease in solution pH in the presence of the LTM (from
290 pH 8.9 to pH 7.6). To a lesser extent, the MOP environment also decreased the Mo concentration for the
291 Cu-based and Zn/Cu-based LTMs in comparison with incubation in water. However, incubation of LTM
292 with rock phosphate or with limestone clearly increased the Mo concentration relative to incubation in
293 water, although alkaline conditions were maintained in these incubations. For the rock phosphate
294 treatments, it is expected that *T*-phosphate precipitation enhanced Mo release. The Mo concentrations

295 obtained with the incubation of the LTM with rock phosphate were higher than for the LTM incubation
 296 in water, and also low *T* concentrations in the solution suggest that this was the result of *T*-phosphate
 297 precipitation (Fig. S4). For the limestone treatments, likely the formation of *T*-carbonate precipitates
 298 enhanced Mo release. Taken together, from these incubation results the Zn-based LTM in combination
 299 with a MOP carrier was the most promising option for further development into a compacted product
 300 with slow-release Mo properties.

301

302

303 Fig. 5: The Mo concentrations (a) and the solution pH (b) after incubation of three LTM materials in water and
 304 macronutrient fertilizer solutions of muriate of potash (MOP), rock phosphate (RP), and limestone. For comparison,
 305 the pH of macronutrient fertilizer solutions without LTM materials is also presented. Error bars represent the
 306 standard error (n=2).

307

308 ***LTM column solubility***

309 The nutrient release characteristics of a compacted pelletized Zn-based LTM-MOP fertilizer were assessed
 310 in a column dissolution test, and compared to those of a reference fertilizer (pelletized amMo-MOP) and

311 a control fertilizer (pelletized MOP) (Fig. 6). The high solubility of the MOP carrier itself was evident in all
312 three treatments, with 90% of the K from the different fertilizers released within 5 h (Fig. 6a). However,
313 for Mo there was a significant difference in the Mo release between the LTM-MOP and amMo-MOP
314 fertilizers. While 90% of Mo was released from the amMo-MOP fertilizer after 4 h, the slow-release
315 characteristics of LTM-MOP were well demonstrated with a rather constant release rate of Mo as a
316 function of time, with only ~32% of Mo released after 72 h. The slight alkaline character of the MOP carrier
317 was evident for the LTM-MOP fertilizer and the MOP control fertilizer, while the eluates from amMo-MOP
318 reference fertilizer were more acidic, likely a result of amMo dissolution (Fig. 6b). In the LTM-MOP
319 treatment, the solution pH proved to be a determining factor for LTM dissolution. During the initial 10 h
320 of the column test, the alkaline solution following MOP dissolution (up to pH 6.8) favored dissolution of
321 Mo with respect to Zn (Fig. 6c), with the Mo:Zn ratio in the eluate exceeding the Mo:Zn ratio in the Zn-
322 based LTM by up to a factor of 3.9. After full dissolution of the MOP carrier, the pH of the eluent decreased
323 and remained within the 6.4-6.5 range, which allowed a congruent dissolution of Mo and Zn. Over the
324 72 h column test, 23% of Zn was released from the LTM phase.

325

326 Fig. 6: The percentage cumulative release of K, Mo and Zn from the three granular fertilizers (a), and the pH of the
 327 eluate solution from each (b), presented as a function of time. Also, for the early stages of the test with the LTM-
 328 MOP fertilizer, the relative Mo/Zn release and the eluate pH are presented as a function of time (c). Error bars
 329 represent the standard error (n=2).

330

331 The column dissolution test confirmed the potential of the compacted LTM-MOP fertilizer to provide a
 332 slow release of Mo. However, with the application of LTM to soils, it is expected that the soil environment

333 will also influence the micronutrient release kinetics in several ways. First, while MOP has a slight alkaline
334 character, the pH of the soil likely largely determines the pH of the fertilizer-soil environment, and can
335 thus affect LTM solubility and micronutrient release according to the results in Fig. 4. Generally, pH values
336 of agricultural soils range between pH 5.0 and 8.0, yet Mo deficiency is more common in acidic soils³³.
337 The solution incubation study showed the lowest Mo solubility for the Zn-based LTM in a MOP
338 environment (Fig. 5), due to the higher pH. However, it is possible that the Cu-based LTMs, which are
339 inherently less soluble, would be more successful at providing a slow micronutrient release in acidic soils
340 compared to Zn-based LTMs. Secondly, adsorption and precipitation of micronutrients released into the
341 soil can enhance the dissolution of the LTM. In acidic soils, Zn and Cu can be fixed through sorption onto
342 oxyhydroxides, while in alkaline soils Zn can be fixed through precipitation with carbonate³⁴. The negative
343 effect of the formation of *T*-carbonate precipitates on the slow-release properties was also demonstrated
344 with the LTM incubation in the presence of limestone (Fig. 5). Possibly, also fixation of Mo through sorption
345 on oxyhydroxides (acidic soils) or precipitation of Mo as CaMoO_4 (alkaline soils) could affect the LTM
346 dissolution in a similar way³⁵. Taken together, future studies on the incubation of LTM-based fertilizers in
347 soils with varying properties are required to determine the full potential of this new slow-release
348 micronutrient fertilizer.

349

350 **Conclusions**

351 This study investigated the use of LTM materials as slow-release fertilizer compounds for Mo while
352 simultaneously providing nutritionally useful Cu and/or Zn. Using a simple co-precipitation procedure, a
353 series of LTM materials was successfully synthesized. The potential of LTM compounds for slow Mo
354 release was demonstrated with a LTM-MOP co-compacted product, which showed promising Mo release
355 characteristics. Further testing in soils and with plant uptake is needed to confirm the desired properties

356 are retained in the soil-plant environment. Furthermore, with continued fertilizer development, also the
357 incorporation of essential cationic micronutrients Mn and Co in LTM fertilizers, and even of Se in the form
358 of SeO_4^{2-} for biofortification purposes, could also be assessed.

359

360 **Supporting Information**

361 The FTIR spectra of the prepared LTMs, SEM micrographs of selected LTM materials, the relative release
362 of Zn, Cu, K and $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ in the water-solubility test, and the concentrations of Zn and Cu after LTM
363 incubation in water and macronutrient fertilizer solutions. This information is available free of charge via
364 the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org/>.

365

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373

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